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Implications Of The Electoral Insecurity On Off-Cycle Elections In Nigeria: A Study Of The November 6, 2021 Governorship Election In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

It is regrettable that since Nigeria got her independence in 1960, elections in Nigeria pose serious Security Challenges, not only in terms of Security of the men and Materials deployed for the elections, but also in terms of protecting the voters and candidates. The heat and passion associated with off-cycle governorship elections in Nigeria often make elections appear like war. The insecurity had led to the death of many politicians, their supporters and innocent citizens. In off-cycle governorship elections in the following states: Anambra, Bayelsa, Kogi, Ekiti, Edo among others, the stories have been the same. The principal obligation of every government is to provide for the welfare and safety of citizens, but that does not appear to be the duty of leaders in Nigeria. The activities of the Indigenous peoples of Biafra (IPOB) and unknown gunmen on the declaration of sit-at-home in the South East geopolitical zone, led to lost of lives and properties and some vehicles seen on the road were set ablaze. Moreover, attempt by some State Governors in the South East to counter the order were unsuccessful at the threat to workers that they stood the risk of losing their salaries if they failed to go to work was not obeyed. Members of IPOB declared one week sit-at-home order on November 4, 2021, just two days to the election, if their leader Nnamdi Kanu who is facing treason trial at Abuja Federal High Court was not released. Due to worsening Security situation in Anambra State ahead of the November 6, 2021 governorship election, the Federal Government threatened to declare a state of emergency in the state through the Attorney General of the Federation (AGF) and Minister of Justice, Abubakar Malami. No fewer than 12 INEC offices in at least seven states were gutted by fire with facilities completely or partially destroyed in the year 2021 by hoodlums. In the last two years, the commission has recorded a total of 41 incidents involving deliberate attacks on the Commission's facilities. Nine of these incidents happened in 2019 and 21 cases in 2020. On the 23rd May, 2021, INEC head office in Awka was attacked by Unknown gunmen who burnt 326 generating sets, six (6) Hilux vehicles, 50% of the non-sensitive materials delivered to the state from INEC Abuja. Stores and collation centres were equally burnt. In the midst of all these insecurity, the commission with the technological innovation including Bimodal Voters Accreditation System (BVAS) conducted free, fair and credible elections in Anambra State. We commend the INCEC, Security agencies and people of Anambra State for a successful elections.

Keywords: Election Insecurity and Off-Cycle Government Elections, Sit-at-home order by IPOB, Bloodshed, Anambra State and Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC).

INTRODUCTION

When Politics is not handled satisfactorily so that a peaceful environment subsists, then security becomes a problem for every citizen. That is why it is expedient for managers or the players of politics to always be very conscious of every step and activity they carry out. They ought to be guided to promote not only harmony in society but also bring and circulate dividends of the end product of politics, which is democracy. Therefore, when politics is played satisfactorily, it brings dividends of democracy, which include stable, conducive and progressive society that is protected by effective and efficient security.

In other words, if politicians fail to practice politics properly, they inadvertently invite insecurity and this impedes progress and development in the society. Do you see a society where there is insecurity? It automatically suggests that democracy has been tempered with and politicians are playing the game in a very dirty way. Security ought to be under the authority of politicians for democracy to thrive but when the opposite becomes the norm, then insecurity is created and there is chaos, destruction and death of innocent citizens. Politicians interfere with electoral processes and create a chaotic, Violent, voting environment that usually results in an insecure atmosphere (Okezie, B. 2021:20). For instance, as Governorship election in Anambra State was drawing nearer, in September 28, 2021, Dr. Chike Akunyili, the husband of Nigeria's former Minister of Information and Culture, Prof. Dora Akunyili, was murdered in cold blood at Nkpor in Idemili North Local Government Area together with his driver and police security aide (Attah 2021:4).

The political class no longer know where to draw the line between them and security agencies. Instead, they throw caution to the wind and meddle with the activities of security agencies, security leaders and their operations. This breeds an insecure environment and perceptions, as being played out in the country today, with agitations for secession spreading like wildfire. Oftentimes, it is the careless decisions of politicians that are usually tainted by ethnic, religious or selfish interests, ignoring the corporate interest of the country when carrying out official assignments that cause trouble. We cannot deny the fact that such inconsiderate policies must have given birth to many of the pockets of insecurity that are weighing down the country today. It is the same with all those agitating about marginalization and non-inclusiveness where appointments are either ethnicized or based on religious affiliation, instead of practising Federal character as enshrined in the constitution.

On the 23rd May 2021, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) Anambra State headquarters office in Awka was set ablaze by Unknown gun men in the most devastating onslaught on the commission's facilities so far. The attackers were systematic and selective in their targets. The pavilion which serves as collation centre during major elections were burnt down and even the stores housing over 326 generating sets and the generating sets were equally burnt. The electric generating sets were recently relocated from the Local Government INEC offices to the state headquarters in the belief that it would be more secure than the Local Government Offices. Similarly, as part of the commission's proactive measures to ensure the success of the Governorship election in November 6, 2021, about 50% of the non-sensitive materials required for the election already delivered to the state were also lost in the fire. In addition, six (6) Utility Vehicles (Toyota Hilux) were set ablaze and the main building substantially damaged and burnt.

It will be recalled that following the fire incident on the eve of the 2019 General Elections in which the Smart Card Readers (SCRs) for the state were burnt, the commission moved the replacement Smart Card Readers from the shipping containers to the concrete store for enhanced Protection. Fortunately, the Smart Card Readers were not affected. Although, no lives were lost these were clearly Orchestrated and targeted attacks aimed at incapacitating the commission in conducting electoral activities especially in Anambra State (Okoye, 2021).

The continuous insecurity and unrestrained attacks on some offices of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) across the country, particularly in the South East and South South geo-political zones is a worrisome development. The affected INEC offices were AkwaIbom (4), Abia (3), Anambra (2), and Imo (2). Some INEC offices had witnessed arson between February 2019 and May 2021 in BOrno, Ebonyi, Jigawa, Kano, Ondo, Plateau, Rivers States, and the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja.

While eleven (11) INEC Offices were reportedly burnt down by hoodlums, eight (8) others were gutted by fire. The incessant and coordinated attacks on INEC facilities across the country portend grave danger to democracy and the polity. There is no doubt that the mindless destruction of INEC facilities will adversely affect the commissions' capacity to conduct elections if the attacks on its facilities persist (Daily Sun Comments, June 1, 2021:11).

Virtually everywhere in the country has been rendered unsafe-North – East, North-Central, North-West, South-East, South-South and the milder South-West. The sit-at-home syndrome declared by the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) every Monday of the week in the South-East contributed to insecurity in the region. How did Anambra descend to this low point, a situation in which people were hunted openly, brutally murdered, and abandoned like animals in the bush? The state had been hijacked by Unknown gun-wielding men who shoot randomly at people without asking questions. The state of insecurity in Anambra state has become leaderless, so insecure and wrecked by violence that everybody was afraid of what would befall them if they step out of homes to go to the market or to walk along the streets or even to exercise.

The way and manner, the three major political Parties, (APC, PDP and APGA), handled their internal democracy in the nomination of their candidates was equally worrisome and created tension in the polity (Anambra State). This non-adherence to democratic rules in the conduct of internal affairs of the political parties in Anambra state was equally responsible for the increase of insecurity in the state, due to the incessant conflict of court judgements from the pre-election of their candidates. A group of International Society for Civil Liberties and Rule of Law (Intersociety) and the Civil Liberties Organisation (CLO) raised alarm over frivolous and discredited court orders on the conducted party primaries by political parties fielding candidates in the Governorship Election, November 6, 2021 in Anambra state. In a joint statement, the Board Chairman of Intersociety (Umeagbalasi 2021:13) warned that the conflicting court judgements, if unchecked and not stopped was capable of scuttling the governorship Poll and denying the conscientious voters in Anambra State their constitutional right to choose their leaders.

With the worsening security situation in Anambra State ahead of the scheduled November 6, 2021, Governorship Election, the Attorney General of the Federation (AGF), and Minister of Justice, Malami (2021:3) stated that the Federal Government may declare a "State of emergency" in the state. He stated further that, no possibility is out ruled by government in terms of ensuring the sanctity of our democratic order, in terms of ensuring that our elections in Anambra state hold, and you cannot out rule possibilities inclusive of the possibility of declaration of state of emergency where it is established, in essence, that there was a failure on the part of the state government to ensure the sanctity of lives, properties and democratic order. The position of the office of the Attorney General, was about the freedom and liberty of movement among others.

The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) without minding the Electoral Insecurity in the state went ahead and prepared for free, fair, credible election. The Director, voter Registry of the Commission, Gambo (2021:13) stated that a total of 2, 525, 471 people cut across the 5, 720 Polling Units, 326 Political Wards and 21 Local Government Areas of the state were eligible to vote in the election. He maintained that, a total of 77, 475 people registered during the 2021 Continuous Voters Registration (CVR) exercise, adding that the 2021 figure represents 3.16 percent increase in the 2019 figure of 2, 447, 996. The Commission resumed the conduct of continuous Voter Registration (CVR) nationwide on the 26th June, 2021, with Online Pre-registration. However, physical person to person registration commenced on 26th July, 2021, and the exercise was further devolved to Registration Area (RA) levels in Anambra state, from 30th August to September 5, 2021.

In terms of age distribution of voters, the middle age group had the highest with 898, 679 representing 34.96 of the total voters; while the aged group (70+) had the lowest figure of 205, 052, representing 8.12 percent of the total voters. In terms of geopolitical spread, a total of 885, 274 representing 35.1 percent of the figure registered in Anambra Central district, a total of 845, 994 representing 33.5 per cent in Anambra North, while a total of 794, 203 representing 31.4 percent registered in Anambra South Senatorial District (Gambo, 2021: 13).

However, given the frightening incidences of killings and destruction of Public buildings and infrastructure that were breaking out like rashes in Anambra State during the run up to the election, many pundits and commentators predicted that rivers of blood would flow through the streets if IPOB insisted on the observance of its lockdown order. The order was lifted a day or two to the polling day and enough Anambrarians showed up at the polling units to keep the flame of democratic mores and practices burning bright – a victory for Democracy. On Wednesday, November 10, 2021, Professor Florence Banku Obi, Vice Chancellor of the University of Calabar and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) Returning Officer for the Anambra Gubernatorial Poll, finally announced the results and declared the winner. This came several hours after the supplementary election was conducted a day before in the Ihiala LGA, the only one among the 21 Local Government Areas of the State where elections did not hold on Saturday, November 6, 2021 (Okoye, 2021:29).

Moreover, Prof. Chukwuma Soludo won 19 out of the 21 Local Government Areas (LGAs), scored at least 25% of the votes cast in all 21 LGAs, and polled nearly half of the total valid votes cast to consign his closest rivals – PDP’s valentine Ozigbo and APC’s Andy Uba – to distant second and third positions respectively. The Governor elect, Prof. Soludo was first drafted into the race in 2010 by powers-that-be in PDP to contest against APGA’s Peter Obi and received a well-deserved shellacking. By a strange twist of fate, Soludo has found himself in APGA just as Obi migrated to PDP. The emergence of Soludo as the winner of the election did not come easy, particularly considering the number of notable Politicians that defected from his Party, APGA, to the rival All Progressives Congress (APC), in the build up to the election. Initially, the defections looked like a joke, but when it became a daily occurrence ahead of the election, many people thought APGA was finished. Leading the defectors to APC were Dr. Nkem Okeke (Deputy Governor of Anambra state), Joy Emordi, Stella Oduah, IFeanyiIbezi, Chukwuma Umeoji, Lynda Ikpeazu, Uche Ekwunife among others (Ujumadu, 2021:12).

Anambra is a State located in South-eastern Nigeria. According to Oral tradition, the title “Anambra” is an anglicised version of the original title “OmaMbala” which is the native name of the Anambra. River which flows through the area being a tributary of the Niger River. The Capital of the state is Awka. Moreover, Onitsha, Ekwulobia, and Nnewi are the biggest commercial and industrial Centers. Anambra state’s slogan is “Light of the Nation”. Anambra state is bounded by Delta State to the West, Imo State to the South, Enugu to the east and Kogi to the north. Most of the population (97%) of Anambra state are members of the Igbo group who are widely known for their determination and great love for entrepreneurship. The Anambra Igbo often move to other states of Nigeria and every region of the World. Wherever they live, their hard work, humility, and entrepreneurial spirit make them stand out in all their activities. That is why Anambra state has the motto: ‘Light of the Nation’. The state was first formed in 1976 from the East-central states, and in 1991 it was considerably reduced in area by an administrative reorganization that created the new state of Enugu (<https://en.m.wikipedia.org>). The present Anambra State was created from the Old Anambra State (which comprised of Enugu and Anambra States) on August 27, 1991 and covers an area of 4, 416 square kilometres with a population of 4, 055, 048 according to 2006 census. They are largely traders and business people and are highly industrious, resourceful and have high communal and self-help spirit. There is a small group of Igala-speaking people in Anambra West Local Government Area of the State.

Theoretical Perspective of Electoral Insecurity in the Off-cycle Elections in Nigeria.

Electoral Insecurity is the state of being open to danger or lack of protection during electoral activities in the discharge of civil responsibility as a voter or as a stakeholders or electoral officials. It is a threat to life and property that is capable of unleashing mayhem on innocent citizen of the country. The principal obligation of every government is to provide for the welfare and safety of citizens since National Security is a moral, Political, Social, Psychological, and economic issue. The tragedy of Nigeria is that criminal groups have coalesced around the failure of national security and they are now making money from people’s misfortunes. It is unfortunate that for years, people have called on the government to take

national security seriously and to protect citizens from deadly attacks by criminal groups but nothing has changed.

In the face of this growing Security Challenge in Nigeria, insurgents are running riot in the North-East, while multiple criminal cartels are killing our citizens, raping our women, destroying agriculture and livelihoods, and even abduction of school children across the country without let or hindrance. The once serene Northern Nigeria and once bubbling southern Nigeria have suddenly become a ghost of themselves, as nowhere is safe anymore. (Okechukwu, 2021:32). For example, who would have imagined that kidnapers, bandits will one day, take more than a hundred students (as hostages), from a boarding school, and ask relatives (of the hostages), to provide rice, beans, palm oil, salt and stock cubes to feed them (in captivity)? This was just to prevent hostages from starving and did not preclude the then ensuing demand for ransom!

The state of insecurity in Anambra State was dire, in which everyone was baffled by the high rate of cold-blooded, murders committed on the streets by unidentified people. In the bid to November 6, 2021 Governorship election in Anambra, the state had been wracked by violence and itinerant gunmen to the election. In reaction to the above, the former Governor of Kwara State, Ahmed (2021:4) lamented on the state of the nation, noting that the high level of nepotism and exclusiveness have given rise to agitations by different ethnic groups. He argued that in 2015, Nigerians overwhelmingly embraced the promise of change. These hopes have not only been dashed, but they have arguably turned out to be the worst Political mistake that has ever been made in this country. Nigeria today appears set to fulfil all the prophecies of doom. Ahmed stressed further on the intractable insecurity in the country and that the unprecedented nepotism and political exclusion have left the country more divided than ever, as evidenced in the various separatist agitations that are threatening the corporate existence of the Country itself.

As Nigeria continues to battle raging insecurity challenges, raging from banditry, kidnapping, murder and terrorism, the unknown gunmen went on rampage in South-East killing, maiming and destroying life and properties. In solidarity with the detention of Nnamdi Kanu, the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) issued a "sit-at-home order" in the South-East to be observed every Monday until Kanu would be released from detention which indirectly affected the preparation of November 6, 2021 Governorship election in Anambra State. For us to understand the growing insecurity in Nigerian elections, it becomes necessary for us to understand the character of the Nigerian State. The Nigerian state has colonial Origin and did not emerge from internal class struggle rather it was imposed from outside by the metropolitan bourgeoisie. At the dawn of independence, those who emerged as leaders formed a collaborative class and having no economic base, they all struggled to get control of the state.

For this research work, the class theory will be used to analyse this work. This is because (Uba, 1984) the state in Nigeria plays a double role which is different from that played by the state in advanced capitalist society.....? the Nigerian state plays double role of being the instrument of the metropolitan bourgeoisie who established it in the first place and principal means of embourgeoisement for the fraction, of nascent petty bourgeoisie who inherited it at independence. What this implies is that Nigerian state does not moderate class struggle rather it is used to harass, intimidate and terrorize the dominated classes in order to play its double role. The state is an organ of class in order to play its double role. The state is an organ class rule, an organ of the oppression of one class by another.

The issue of Electoral Insecurity during the governorship election, November 6, 2021 was a case of intra-class struggle of who dominate and control the state power in Awka, Anambra state. The conduct of Party primaries, gave rise to this insecurity as the three major political Parties in Anambra State, the APC, PDP and APGA did not follow the democratic principles in the conduct of the Party Primaries and the end product was the multiple court cases before the election. Nwosu (2021:10) stated that, everybody in Anambra state and Nigeria witnessed what happened in the state as far as the Party Primaries of APGA, APC and PDP were concerned. He further said that these parties have shown gross indiscipline and leadership deficits, which manifested in the ways they conducted their Party primaries ahead of the governorship election in the state. What happened in APC primary was an ambush? The Party opted for a

direct Primary but at the end of the day, a candidate emerged without anything like primary taking place anywhere. This is a violation of the APC Constitution and the Electoral Act. For APGA, the Party had three factions, producing the candidates through three different processes. Apart from going contrary to APGA Constitution, APGA also went against the Electoral Act in the conduct of their primaries, so INEC was right when it said that there was no clear Congress that produced delegates for APGA primary. Nwosu maintained that for PDP, the story was the same. This is because, every day, the Party continues to change techniques of doing their primary. Today, they will say ad-hoc delegates, tomorrow, super delegates, the next nominal delegates.

(a) The All Progressive Grand Alliance (APGA) Ruling Party Perspective/Interests.

The theoretical Perspective of the Party, All Progressive Grand Alliance (APGA) is that, it is the Anambrarians Party founded on the principles of equity, justice, peace and fair play for the people of Anambra state. In reference to the above Party Perspective, the National Chairman of the Party, APGA, Oye (2021:8) opined that the truths of the matter is that APGA is indestructible and boasted that APGA will win the election because nobody can wrestle with the Lord. He insisted that anybody who fights APGA will be destroyed, because God brought Soludo to succeed Obiano successfully.

In support of the above Party perspective, the Governor-elect, Soludo (2021:8) during the inauguration of his campaign Council in Awka, Anambra state, stressed that Anambra is APGA and APGA is Anambra. He said the procurement of Court rulings from outside Anambra State was aimed at stopping APGA in Anambra State. According to the former Governor of Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), it is wrong for somebody to go for screening in APGA, pay the necessary fees to the APGA National Chairman, go for screening and lose and then appoint his own Chairman and go to Jigawa State High Court to say that this is now the national Chairman. It could be recalled that on June 16, 2021, ALhaji Rabieyu Garba Aliyu, an indigene and resident of Jigawa State, approached the Jigawa State High Court and Sought relief from the Court to be declared the acting national Chairman of the All Progressive Grand Alliance (APGA). His contention was that he, rather than Chief Jude Okeke, was the rightful person for the seat, following the suspension of Chief Edozie Njoku by the National Executive Committee of the Party on June 15, 2021.

Justice Musa Ubale, before whom case was filed on June 30, 2021, gave his judgement in the case and found in favour of Okeke as the rightful Chairman of the Party with powers to Conduct governorship primaries of the Party including that of Anambra state, which the plaintiff sought as his right to conduct. Barely a week later, on July 6, 2021 Chief P.N. Ikwueto, on behalf of Chief Victor Oye and APGA, filed a notice of appeal and also motion seeking leave of the court to appeal as an interested person. Also Edozie Njoku, the national Chairman whom the plaintiff claimed was suspended by the NEC of the Party, acting through Chike Onyemenam, also filed his motion seeking leave to appeal as an interested person on July 22, 2021. The plaintiff in the suit filed his own appeal through Chibuzor Ezike on June 30, 2021, the same day the judgement was delivered. The Courts in Nigeria being on their annual vacation and the case being on election-related case, the president of the Court of Appeal set up a panel of three justices, headed by Hon. Justice Haruna Simon Tsammani. Other members of the special appeal panel were Justice Usman Musale and Justice Abdullahi Ridwan Maiwada (Nduka: 2021: 22).

The intra-class struggle in the Party (APGA) was to determine the authentic flag bearer of the Party in November 6, 2021 governorship election in Anambra State. In reaction to the above struggle, a member of the Board of the All Progressive Grand Alliance (APGA), Ezeonwuka (2021:10) lamented that the leadership of the Party would not allow intruders to hijack its Primary election, because the Party nominated the former CBN governor Prof. Charles Chukwuma Soludo, as its candidate and expressed worry that people jumped through the window to hijack the process. He further said that the Victor Oye led executive was in charge of APGA and that the Oye executive came through the door and elected Prof. Soludo through the front door and the Party cannot allow intruders coming through the window to take over the Party.

This challenge or intra-struggle of who becomes the national Chairman and flag bearer of the Party was finally decided by the apex Court. On October 14, 2021 the Supreme Court in a Unanimous decision by a five-man panel of Justices, Voided the judgement of a Jigawa State High Court, which made a

consequential order that sacked the Chief Victor Oye-led National working Committee (NWC), of APGA, and recognized Chief, Jude Okeke as the Acting National Chairman of the Party. Justice Musa Ubale of the Jigawa State High Court had in the judgement he delivered on June 30, in suit No. JDU/022/2021, ordered the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC), to only recognize the Okeke – led fraction of the Party which conducted a parallel Primary election that produced Chief Chukwuma Umeoji as APGA’s candidate for the governorship elections poll. The high court judgement was however voided on August 10, 2021 by the Kano Division of the Court of Appeal which reinstated the Chief Oye-led NWC of the Party that Organised the primary election that produced Soludo. The appellate Court, in a Unanimous decision by a three-man panel of justices led by Justice Harunaalsammani, maintained that the Jigawa State High Court lacked the territorial jurisdiction to entertain a matter relating to the leadership of a political Party. It, therefore, voided the consequential order that was issued against APGA leadership under Oye. Dissatisfied with the Verdict, Okeke, who was previously the Deputy National Chairman (South) of APGA, took the matter before the Supreme Court, where he lost (Omonobi, k, Ujumadu, V etal, 2021:24).

After months of tension occasioned by insecurity and killings by Unknown gunmen and fears that the Anambra state Governorship election might not hold, the election was finally concluded with the candidate of APGA, Professor Chukwuma Soludo emerging as winner. He polled 112, 229 votes, won 19 of the 21 local government councils and got 25 per cent of the votes cast in the two councils he lost to be declared Governor-elect by the Chief Returning Officer of the Poll, Professor Florence Banku Obi. Moreover, Valentine Ozigbo of the Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) his closest challenger scored 53, 807 Votes. However, Prof. Soludo’s 112, 229 votes is 17, 065 votes less than the 129, 294 votes scored by the 17 candidates that contested with him. The contest has been adjudged as peaceful, free and fair but critics insist it would have been better except technical issues on the part of the INEC and insecurity which made the exercise not to be held in many places (Ndujihe, 2021:4).

Prof. Chukwuma Soludo is indeed a pragmatist, a technocrat, and a brilliant first class economist full of radical social ideas and developmental models. He had made three attempts to win the governorship starting from 2010, by jumping from APGA to PDP, and eventually back to APGA, he resisted being compartmentalised as an ideologue. Had he remained principled, he would not have won the seat today. But had he not been persistent and ideologically flexible, he would not have made mincemeat of the APC.

(b) The All Progressives Congress (APC) Party Perspective/Interest.

The All Progressives Congress (APC) is a political Party that has a process of nominating its candidates for elections, and for the Anambra governorship, the party opted for the direct Primary election which is in line with its Constitution. The direct primary election is like a general election where all Card carrying members cast their votes. The primary election is an internal business of the Party and the Party’s decision is Supreme. Nwosu (2021:21) described what happened in APC primary as an ambush. He argued that the Party Opted for a direct primary but at the end of the day, a candidate emerged without anything like primary taking place anywhere which is a violation of the APC Constitution and the Electoral Act.

All the who-is who in APC in the State have said in diverse ways that no primary election was held in any of the 326 electoral wards of the state on June 26, 2021, including Andy Uba’s Uga ward of Aguata Local Government Area of the State. However, Senator Ngige, Moghalu, Dr. Chidozie Nwankwo and Chief Azuka pointed out that Primary election did not take place in any designated centres in Anambra State. The whole 13 other aspirants were firm on it that no primary election of any sort was held in any part of the state that day. None till date could guess the colour or size of the ballot papers/boxes. So, if that was the case, where did Governor Abiodun of Ogun State arrived at the figures he read out? Who are the Officers that worked with him? Where and where did any of them operate that day? Who were the local staff that worked with them? The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) Anambra State, in a reaction to the above, the Election and Party Monitoring (EPM) department of the Commission, testified that contrary to the results announced by the Abiodun-led Anambra Governorship Election (Collins 2021: 16) the primary did not hold in any of the 326 wards in the state.

The Abuja division of the Federal High Court on December 20, 2021, nullified the participation of the All Progressives Congress (APC) and its candidate, Andy Uba in the November 6 Governorship Election in Anambra State. Justice Inyang Ekwo gave the judgement in a suit filed by the governorship aspirant of the Party, Chief George Moghalu challenging the process and outcome of the June 26, 2021 primary of the APC that produced Uba as its candidate. Justice Ekwo who agreed with the plaintiff held that the June 26, 2021, primary of the APC which produced Uba as its candidate was not validly conducted. He also ruled that the primary breached the provisions of the Electoral Act and the APC guidelines for the conduct of the exercise. The Judge said the plaintiff had successfully demonstrated that the Primary was not conducted in accordance with the law and the Party's guidelines. Therefore, the case of the plaintiff succeeds on its merit. The Judge therefore declared that the APC had no candidate in the Anambra governorship election by the non-inclusion of the name of Moghalu in the primary and the conduct of the poll in contravention of the Electoral Act and the Party's guidelines. Ekwo held that since the primary was conducted illegally APC (1st defendant) cannot be a beneficiary of the November 6 gubernatorial election which produced the All Progressives Grand Alliance (APGA) Candidate, Prof. Charles Soludo as winner. Ekwo, who described the conduct of the primary by APC as crude and primitive entered that the 22.5 million paid by Moghalu as expression of interest and nomination forms be refunded to him since the party failed to comply with the provisions of the law and its guidelines. Moghalu had in July 2021 filed the suit at the Court, seeking an order removing Uba and APC from the list of gubernatorial candidates and Political Parties Partaking in the Anambra governorship election on the grounds that the party had failed to conduct a valid primary (Godwin, 2021:7).

APC in Anmbra State remains divided with one faction loyal to the Minister of Labour and Employment, Dr. Chris Ngige, and another led by Senator Andy Uba, the governorship candidate of the party in November 6, 2021 election. This latter group, going by the APC rule book, is regarded as the authentic group, as the rules stipulate that the governorship candidate of the Party is the leader of its caucus in such state. However, Chris Ngige kicked against the processes that threw up the Party's governorship candidate in the state, Uba and thereafter distanced himself from the Party's quest to win the election. Ngige was accused of not putting the required efforts as a leader, in the quest by the Party to win the governorship seat in the run up to the election. They further stated that it was not only about the recent Party primary but the attitude of the Minister, which he had also exhibited over time. According to them, in the governorship election that had Hon. Tony Nwoye as candidate in 2017, Ngige neither worked with nor openly campaigned for him (Osemedua, 2021:21).

The APC national ruling Party, Nigeria's supposedly Progressive Party, reposed enormous confidence in the defections they had conjured before the November Poll, and the electoral temper and atmosphere they had specialized in creating. The leading defectors to APC were Dr. NkemOkeke, the Deputy Governor of Anambra State, Joy Emordi, the Senator Stella Oduah, Ifeanyi Ibezi, Chukwuma Umeoji, Lynda Ikpeazu, Senator Uche Ekwunife, among others. The candidate of APC, Senator Andy Uba, who was enjoying the euphoria of the defections, believed that APGA might collapse before the election, but all had become history as APGA swept the Poll by winning in 19 local government areas and scoring and getting 25% of the votes in the remaining two. It should also not be forgotten that Senator Andy Uba, the Candidate of APC, lost his local government to Soludo and did not win any local government during the election.

(c) The Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) Party Perspective/Interests

Peoples Democratic Party (PDP) was formed in 1998 and dubbed the largest Political Party in Africa and arguably emerged with so much promise for the country. But its history in 23 years has had a momentum of classic drama, a familiar smell, a downward trajectory that breaks the heart and tears the umbrella that supposed to be a shelter and Unity for a common good. In fact, the history of the party particularly as it concerns the position of its national Chairman gives little crumb for comfort. Consider this: from 1998 to date, PDP has had 14 National Chairmen. This means an average of 18 months for each. Check out the names: Dr. Alex Ekwueme (1998), Solomon Lar (1998-1999), Barnabas Gemade (1999-2001), Audu Ogbah (2001-2005), Col. Almadu Ali (2005-2008), Prince Vincent Ogbulafor (2008-2010), Dr. Okwesilieze Nwodo (2010), Dr. Haliru Mohammed (2010), Alhaji kawu Baraje (2011-2014), Dr.

Bamanga Tukur (2012-2014), Adamu Muazu (2014-2015), Senator Ali Modu Sheriff (2015-2016), Ahmed Makarfi (2015-2016), Uche Secondus (2017-2021), Ayu (2021 till Date). What is responsible for this high turnover of its National Chairman? Lack of internal democracy and lack of Vision, because when a party lacks internal cohesion, and vision, it lacks the Oxygen to sustain success and the Political life to move the nation forward (Onwukwe, 2021:12).

The intra-class struggle of the governorship aspirants who aspired to be the flag bearer of the Party created tension and crisis in the Party during and after the Primary election. There were about four different cases arising from the June 26, 2021, Primary election of the Party such as Edwin Akwuobi, Nwosu Amaechi, Obumneme Jeff and Chukwudi Onochie Vs PDP and INEC – A State High Court sitting in Awka, Anambra State Capital barred the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) from accepting any individual presented by PDP as its governorship candidate until the outcome of a suit brought before it is determined. A parallel candidate of the Party for the November 6, 2021 Poll in the State, Senator Ugochukwu Uba had dragged INEC, PDP and Valentine Ozigbo before the Court in a Suit Marked A/230/2021, praying among others, for the nullification of the Poll which produced Ozigbo as the flag bearer of PDP. The Presiding Judge, Justice O. A. Nwabunike on July 6, 2021, Ordered INEC not to accept anybody presented as the candidate of the second defendant, the PDP, until the determination of the outcome of the suit (Odogwu, and Mkwugwu, 2021:10).

While some of the statutory delegates were in Court seeking an invalidation of the Primary election and its outcome on the grounds that the election was not properly constituted, leading to their disenfranchisement as against the provision of Article 25(1), (2), (3) and (4) of the PDP Constitution, Hon. Ekwochi already secured an Order of Court to the effect that “nobody should take any further step pending the hearing and determination of both the motion on notice and the originating summons”. In reaction to the above, the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) on July 15, 2021, Published the list of candidates for the November 6, 2021 governorship election in Anambra State. It left the space for the candidate of PDP blank. Reason: INEC said it obeyed Court Orders. Note, it did not say Order but Orders. This is an indication that there were various Court pronouncements on the process that led to the selection of a candidate for PDP, and also on the candidature of a candidate for PDP, and also on the candidature of the “Victor” at the election. (Uchegbu, 2021:16). However, later Valentine Ozigbo was cleared by Court as the Flagbearer of PDP to contest the November 6, 2021 governorship election in Anambra State.

The PDP flagbearer, Valentine Ozigbo scored 53, 807 votes in the November 6, 2021 governorship election to become the closest Challenger of Prof. Soludo of APGA, the winner of the election. There is always a certain cockiness about first-class brains that makes them so self-confident, if not actually arrogant. Prof. Soludo’s first runner-up, Valentine Ozigbo, another first-class brain, would have been as showy and self-assured, instead of mortified, had he won the Poll for the PDP. Cultured, intelligent and cosmopolitan, he found the good nature to congratulate the APGA Candidate, believing sensibly that such display of noblesse Oblige does not diminish him in any way.

Looking at Ozigbo closely, he comes across as a man of rare quality, uniquely different. He has the commanding self-confidence to make things run more smoothly and efficiently. He is not a man who deludes himself that brain is everything, even though, he is by all standards, outstandingly brilliant. There are of course, entire libraries of books that analyse key leadership qualities, but most are rather academic in their approach, or indeed, limited by a single author’s perspective. If you want to know what makes someone a rare quality, whether he has a higher purpose, go directly to the source. Ozigbo said he wants to change the wrong perception of many people about Politics. That is what men of ideas do: they are doers, not just thinkers. Truth is, there is a lot one person can do if he assembles the right people to work with him. Ozigbo is an astute banker, financial expert by training, the best and brightest in his class, he became one of the best sought after talents in the banking industry, a chevening scholar before Transcorp came calling. He worked there for seven years with sterling achievements and was elevated to the position of President and CEO (Onwukwe 2021:12).

(d) The Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) Perspective/Interests

The Kenny Okwu Kanu, better known as Nnamdi Kanu, is a young man who possesses a gift that many people wished they had: a gift of conviction of the people. When he talks, you cannot help but listen. A gift of propaganda in the mould of Paul Joseph Goebbels, the German Nazi Politician, who was the Chief propagandist for the Nazi Party from 1933, through to the end of the Second World War in 1945. When they say white is black, people believe them. Nnamdi Kanu succeeded in convincing a good proportion of Nigerians that our President Muhammedu Buhari is dead, that the one in Aso Rock Villa today, is dead, that the one in Aso Rock Villa today, is an impostor called Jubril Sudani, from Sudan. Many Ordinary folks still believe this lie till today. That is how powerful Nnamdi Kanu can be with words. He could make people do incredible things, some are very ready to die for him (Ikhioya, 2021:18).

The perspective of the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB) is the movement for the actualisation of the Sovereign State of Biafra. The Igbos are denied fair, just and equitable treatment in Nigeria as presently constituted. However, the marginalisation and exclusion became worse and peaked to provocative level under this Buhari administration. Kanu and his group, the Indigenous People of Biafra (IPOB), have for years been protesting against this ill treatment and demanding for a Biafra Republic. Their self-determination activities have been peaceful across the world, with members of the group marching through the streets and to embassies, to make their demands. This was going on until Nigerian Security officials began to attack them while dispersing their peaceful processions. Things got worse when the home of IPOB leader was attacked in 2017 while he was on bail after two years detention in Abuja prison. The attack raised tensions between IPOB members and the Government. Kanu fled the country and continued to coordinate his members from there (Okoli, Ujumadu and Agbo et al 2021:48).

The agitation by pro-Biafra groups for the actualization of the dream republic recently got to an anti-climax when the arrowhead in the agitation, Mazi Nnamdi Kanu, the leader of the Indigenous People of Biafra, (IPOB) was allegedly abducted in Kenya and delivered to Nigeria, then detained by the Department of State Security Service (DSS), in Abuja. Kanu, it would be recalled was facing trial in an Abuja High Court before he left the Country under controversial circumstances following attack on his Afaraukwu, Umuahia Country home in in Abia State by some Military men. His first appearance at the Court for the renewed trial witnessed a large assemblage of Biafran Supporters and Security Operatives had a hectic time controlling the crowd. The case was later adjourned and Kanu was remanded in DSS Custody. On the adjourned date, the Court premises was filled to capacity by members of IPOB and Lawyers who wanted to catch a glimpse of Kanu, but this was not to be as he was not brought to court.

The non-appearance of Kanu in Court infuriated members of IPOB who, through media and publicity secretary of the group, Comrade Emma Powerful, declared that every Monday would henceforth be declared “Sit-at-home” until Kanu is released from detention. Generally, Igbo people being business inclined do not joke with Mondays because as the first business day of the week, it is assumed that what happens on the first day of business of the week would go a long way to determine the shape of things for that week. Usually, Igbo businessmen, therefore, look forward to doing good business on Mondays as such cities like Onitsha, Aba, Enugu, Owerri, Umuahia, Awka witness influx of traders from other parts of the Country to transact businesses. So, when IPOB declared the first Monday sit-at-home on August 9th, 2021, the entire Igbo nation was jotted. Before that date, the IPOB propaganda machinery was at its best with threats that anyone who dared leave his house that day would have himself or herself to blame. In fact, death threats were issued to the people and even security Operatives in that regard. The IPOB directive insisted that the weekly sit-at-home would be in force until Nnamdi Kanu was released unconditionally by the Federal Government (Ujumadu, 2021:17).

The Sit-at-home turned the entire south East into a ghost Zone as it was totally obeyed and nobody, not even government Officials, dared leave their houses. Commercial activities were totally paralyzed and at the end of the day, losses incurred as a result of the sit-at-home was put at billions of naira. Even the NECO examination scheduled for the day was missed by most Students because they could not go school to write the exam in the South East. In some states, such as Imo, Anambra, Enugu and Ebonyi, lives were lost and some vehicles seen on the road were set ablaze. Attempt by some state governors in the South-East to counter the Order were unsuccessful as the threat to workers that they stood the risk of losing their salaries if they failed to go to work that Monday, was not obeyed. Some people who depend on their daily work to feed their families were the

hardest hit during the sit-at-home as their families could not put food on their table that day. Those who risked it by trying to do something to be able to feed their families had unpalatable stories to tell as suspected IPOB members threw their articles of trade into the drainages for daring to disobey the order.

The IPOB Perspectives equally affected the Preparation for Electoral activities in Anambra State for the conduct of November 6, 2021 governorship election. The sit-at-home of the group instil fear in the adhoc staff trained for th conduct of the governorship election and many of them abandoned the job due to fear of unknown. They were equally of the Opinion that the Anambra State governorship election should not be conducted in Anambra which is Biafran land. The IPOB argued that the Nigerian government should heed now to the voice of reason coming from within Nigeria and from outside the shores of Nigeria to Unconditionally free their leader, Mazi Nnamdi Kanu, and announce a date for Biafra referendum or plebiscite where their people will choose where they wish to belong before it is too late.

RESEARCH MATERIAL AND METHOD

A research design is a scientific logic that has a link with the data collected with appropriate analytical tools already specified and adopted under Methodology. The discussion constitutes a major task that would largely determine the relevance of the work (Obasi, 1999:106). However, in a descriptive study such as this, its finding must be credible. The key criterion or principle of a good documentary research is found in the motion of trustworthiness and neutrality of its findings or decision (Bouma and Ling, 2004). Just as a quantitative study cannot be considered valid unless it passes reliability and credibility tests: Trustworthiness entails credibility and transferability, which is the extent to which the findings can be explored in another context (Bassegy, 1981:73-94). These qualities of a good methodology will help to explain the roles and involvement of different stakeholders and Security agencies in the Conduct of November 6, 2021, Governorship election in Anambra State. This thesis will help us to know whether their involvement undermined the credibility of the governorship election in Anambra State. The technique of content analysis will be used to draw some relevant information or facts that will help validate the research. The technique is a scientific means or process of analysing or comprehending information or facts scientifically. It is a universal process of carrying out a research work in order to generate a detailed knowledge of the work under study. This technique will be used to analyse data collected.

Table 1: Content Analysis

S/No	Speech/Interview	Number of Paragraphs	Electoral Insecurity in off-cycle Elections in Nigeria
1	The interview of former senior special Assistant on Public Affairs to former President Goodluck Jonathan, Doyin Okupe, "What Nigeria must do to end Insecurity", <i>Daily Sun</i> , October 14, 2021, P. 21	8	7
2	The interview of the former speaker of House of Representatives, Ghali Umar Na'Abba, :Why insecurity persists in Nigeria:, <i>Daily Sun</i> , July 21, P. 13	10	9
3	The speech of the Attorney General of the Federation (AGF) and Minister of Justice, Abubakar Malami, "Insecurity:" FG threatens to declare emergency rule in Anambra", <i>New Telegraph</i> , October, 7, 2021, P. 1-3.	13	11
4	The interview of Senator Shehu Sani, "Bandits worse Security risk than IPOB, Igboho," <i>Daily Sun</i> , August 3, 2021, P. 13.	10	7
5	The speech of the National Commissioner and Chairman Information, Voter Education and Publicity Committee, Festus Okoye, "Gundmen's Attack on INEC Awka Office, huge setback for guber Poll-INEC," <i>Daily Sun</i> , August, 10, 2021, P.10	9	8
6	The interview of Director General, Voice of Nigeria (VON), "Imposition, Impunity Cost APC Anambra Governorship," <i>Saturday Sun</i> , November 13, 2021, P. 24	11	9
Total		61	51

From the table above, the empirical research shows that out of 61 paragraphs that focused on the conduct of governorship election in Anambra State, 51 emphasized on the issue of Electoral Insecurity in Anambra governorship election, where the sit-at-home order by IPOB turned the entire South East into a ghost zone as it was totally obeyed and nobody, not even government officials dared leave their houses. Commercial activities here totally paralyzed and at the end of that day, losses incurred as a result of the sit-at-home was put at billions of naira. Moreover, people who depend on their daily work to feed their families were the hardest hit during the sit-at-home as their families could not put food on their table. However, those who risked it by trying to do something to be able to feed their families had unpalatable stories to tell as suspected IPOB members threw their articles of trade into the drainages for daring to disobey the order. It could be recalled that non-appearance of Nnamdi Kanu in Court by government infuriated members of IPOB to declare that every Monday would henceforth be declared sit-at-home until Kanu was released. In Anambra State, lives were lost and some vehicles seen on the road were set ablaze. An attempt by the Anambra State government to counter the order were unsuccessful as the threat to workers that they stood the risk of losing their salaries if they failed to go to work that Monday, was not obeyed.

The Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) places utmost importance in planning and keeping to timeliness for the conduct of elections. On the basis of this, the commission pre-delivered over 50% of the non-sensitive materials for the conduct of the election well ahead of time. But the unknown gunmen constituted themselves as a clog in their wheel of progress in the preparation for the governorship Poll in Anambra State INEC Office as they set the office ablaze, destroying buildings, equipment, 50% of the non-sensitive materials and utility vehicles (hilus vans -7). They also burnt the INEC collation centre, a store housing 300 generators among others.

Understanding the challenges of Pre-2017 and 2021 Off-Cycle Governorship Election and Electoral Instability in Nigeria.

Insecurity is the State of being open to danger or threat or lack of protection of human life and properties. The success or failure of any election is dependent on effective security and it is a state of environment which guarantees freedom from threat, intimidation and anxiety. Jega (2012:1) stated that the heat and passion associated with election in Nigeria often make elections appear like war. Pre-election violence has led to the death of many Politicians, their supporters and innocent citizens. It is not therefore surprising that elections in Nigeria pose serious Security Challenges not only in terms of Security of the men and materials deployed for the elections, but also in terms of protecting the voters and candidates.

Electoral Security is crucial for creating the proper environment, electoral staff required to carry out their duties, for voters to freely go to their polling Units to Vote, for candidates and Political Parties to organise rallies, and campaigns and for other numerous stakeholders to discharge their responsibilities under the constitution and the Electoral Act. Adequate Security ensures the free movement of electoral Staff, Voters, Candidates, Observers and other stakeholders on Election Day, which, in turn adds to the credibility of the electoral process. Similarly, adequate security is an important pre-condition for the deployment of valuable electoral assets and sensitive materials to registration and Polling sites.

With the conduct of the Pre-2017 Governorship Primaries in Anambra State for the conduct of November 18, 2017 Governorship election, the stage was set for the battle before the main elections as many of the primaries were enmeshed in one crises or the other. During the Political Primaries while some aspirants walked out of the venues, others complained of lack of transparency and outright Manipulations and given strong considerations to pitching tent with the opposition. Yet, a number of aggrieved aspirants took to legal options.

In 2017 Governorship primaries of the APGA was bedevilled with parallel primaries in the State. The faction led by the National Chairman of the Party, Victor Oye led their governorship primaries on August 15, 2017 at Prof. Dora Akunyili women development centre, Awka where the incumbent Governor, Chief Willie Obiano was re-elected the flag bearer of the Party for the November 18, 2017 Governorship election. The other fractional group was led by Chief Martin Agbaso held their Own factional

governorship primary at Orumba South Local Government Area where Mr. Hygers Igwebuike was elected as APGA flag bearer for November 18, 2017 election.

In PDP and APC, the stories were similar in their respective governorship primaries. There was mild drama on August 28, 2017, the venue of PDP governorship primaries after the counting of Votes, one of the aspirants Ifeanyi Ubah collected the microphone in protest of the manner the primary was organized, in favour of Oseloka Obaze and rejected the outcome/result of the exercise (Anyanwu, 2017: 44). Another aspirant, Senator Stella Oduah alleged that her absence in the Venue of the Primary was because of the imposition of candidates on the state chapter of the Party. The result of the governorship primary in APC was rejected by some other aspirants who alleged it was imposition of Tony Nwoye on the Party for instance, Andy Ubah rejected the outcome and took a legal option against the Party (Obogo, 2017:1).

The United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and the UK Department for International Development (DFID) validated the final result declared by the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) on Anambra State Governorship election held on November 18, 2017. They opined that the voters should have confidence on INEC's Official results for the Anambra 2017 gubernatorial election because it reflects the ballots cast at the Polling Units (Jibueze, 2017:3). The incumbent Governor Willie Obiano of the All Progressive Grand Alliance (APGA) won the November 18, 2017 governorship election convincingly. He defeated his opponents in all the 21 Local Government Areas with 234, 071 votes, representing 55.42 per cent of the total valid votes cast. The APC flag bearer in the race, Dr. Tony Nwoye trailed him with 98, 752 votes while Mr. Oseloka Obaze of the PDP followed closely with 70, 293 votes. The Chief Returning Officer and the Vice Chancellor of the University of Calabar, Prof.ZanaAkpogu declared that Willie Obiano have satisfied the requirements of the law and is hereby declare winner (Mordi and Nwanosike, 2017:2).

In November 6, 2021 governorship election in Anambra State, the three major Political Parties in the State, APGA, APC and PDP, had internal democracy crises which manifested in the ways they conducted their party primaries ahead of the election. It is a fact, that many citizens, including Party leaders, governors, senators and other categories of Political actors do not know the aim or purpose for Party Primaries. These three political parties had different conflicting court cases arisen from the primaries.

In reaction to the conflicting decisions by Courts on the issue of party primaries, the Chief Justice of Nigeria, (CJN) Justice Ibrahim Tanko Muhammad (2021, 17) On August 30, 2021, summoned six (6) Chief Judges of State High Courts in a bid to halt the indiscriminate granting of orders and injunctions by some judges and to arrest the glaring descent to judicial anarchy and disrepute. These invited to appear before the National Judicial Council (NJC) included the Chief Judges of Rivers, Anambra, Jigawa, Kebbi, Imo and Cross River States. While those of Imo, Jigawa and Anambra states were to explain the roles of their Courts in pre-election cases relating to the Anamba governorship election, those of Rivers Kebbi and Cross River were to speak on their court's handling of the cases relating to the status of the Chairman of PDP, Prince Uche Second us.

The Inspector General of Police, Usman Alkali Baba deployed 34, 587 Officers, Special Forces and three helicopters for the Poll. The assurance from the electoral Umpire and the Police came as the Supreme Court cleared the coast for former Governor of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Prof. Chukwuma Soludo, to contest the election as the candidate of the All Progressive Grand Alliance (APGA). There was jubilation in various parts of Anambra State on October 14, 2021, after the News filtered in that the Supreme Court had ruled that Chief Victor Oye was the authentic National Chairman of APGA, and therefore had the authority to nominate the governorship candidate of the Party for the election. The APGA faithful commended the judiciary for their doggedness in defending the cause of democracy against those whose activities were inimical to national development and ethos. Moreover, based on Election Security Threat Analysis Conducted by the Force Intelligence Bureau, Force headquarters developed a "Strategic Election Security Operation Order" which will involve the mobilization and deployment of a total of 34, 587 Police Personnel comprised of Conventional Police Officers, Police Mobile Force (PMF), Counter Terrorism Unit (CTU), Special forces Personnel, Explosives Ordinance Unit (EOD), Force Intelligence Bureau (FIB), INTERPOL Special Protection Unit (SPU) as well as

Police Medical Teams for credible electoral process in the state (Omonobi, Umumadu, et al, 2021: 15-26).

On Wednesday November 10, 2021, Prof. Florence Banku Obi, Vice Chancellor of the University of Calabar and the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) Returning Officer for the Anambra Governorship Election, finally announced the results and declared the winner. This came several hours after the supplementary election was conducted a day before in the Ihiala Local Government Area, the only one among the 21 Local Government Areas of the State where elections did not hold on Saturday, November 6, 2021 (Okoye, 2021: 29) The Governor-elect Charles Chukwuma Soludo won 19 out of the 21 Local Government Area (LGAs) Scored at least 25% of the votes cast in all 21 local government areas and polled nearly half of the total valid votes cast to consign his closest rivals – PDP’s Valentine Ozigbo and APC’s Andy Uba- to distant second and third positions respectively. The success of the Anambra Poll, despite many hitches, was certainly not because of the simplistic manner the Federal Government Overwhelmed the state with Security agencies. Kogi was similarly overwhelmed, but the country had not yet witnessed the demystification brought upon law enforcement agencies by the EndSARS phenomenon, nor the rampart killings that bled them in many parts of the South East. INEC was better in Organising the Anambra election than it was accustomed to, but it was not responsible for the Overall success of the Poll.

The United State Government said that the result of the just Concluded Anambra governorship election was a reflection of the will of the people. They noted the tremendous challenges faced by INEC and Security force personnel on the ground and commend the efforts that led to secure election with a credible outcome. The conference of Nigeria Political Parties (CNPP) while congratulating Soludo praised the INEC for the transparent conduct of the Poll and for allowing the wish of the people to prevail. A team of election observer groups that monitored the Anambra governorship Poll on November 6 and November 9, 2021, described the election as successful, adding however that the malfunctioning of the Bimodal voters Accreditation system (BVAS), almost marred the efforts and preparations made by the INEC. Also, the Inter Party Advisory Council (IPAC), commended Prof. Soludo for his resounding and well deserved victory. Congratulating Soludo, President Buhari in a message issued by his special Adviser on media and Publicity, Chief Femi Adesina praised Security agencies for their determination to ensure the election went on as smoothly as possible, and the INEC for the successful conclusion of the exercise, despite initial challenges. Soludo’s closest challenger in the election, Mr. Val Ozigbo of the PDP, congratulated the winner and hailed all the contestants in the election. Similarly, Mr. Peter Obi congratulated Prof. Soludo on winning the gubernatorial election: Also, the Minister of Labour and Employment, Senator Chris Ngige, in a goodwill message issued by his Media Office, congratulated Soludo, saying it was a victor well deserved (Okoli, Ndujihe et al, 2021:35).

The INEC Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS) is a system for accrediting voters using fingerprint and facial recognition technology which was used as a test run in the governorship election in Anambra State. It was also used to scan and upload Polling Units result sheets to the INEC Result viewing (IReV) Portal: www.inecelctionresults.com. The Official INEC results for 2021 Anambra Gubernatorial Election of the four (4) top scoring Political Parties are as follows:

Table 2: The Results of 2021 Governorship Election in Anambra State

S/No	LGA	APC	APGA	PDP	YPP
1	AWKA SOUTH	2595	12, 891	5498	919
2	DUNUKOFIA	1991	4124	1680	1360
3	OYI	2830	6133	2484	900
4	ANYAMELUM	2409	3424	2804	407
5	ANA OCHA	2085	6911	5108	868
6	ANAMBRA EAST	2034	9747	1380	559
7	IDEMILI SOUTH	1039	2312	2016	752
8	ONITSHA SOUTH	2050	4281	2253	271
9	NJIKOKA	3216	8803	3409	924
10	NNEWI NORTH	1278	3369	1511	6485
11	ORUMBA NORTH	2060	4394	1672	887
12	OGBARU	1178	3051	3445	484
13	ONITSHA NORHT	3909	5587	3781	682
14	AGUATA	4773	9136	3798	1070
15	IHAIALA	343	8283	2485	344
16	IDIMILI NORTH	2291	5358	2312	902
17	EKWUSIGO	1237	2570	1857	727
18	ORUMBA SOUTH	2672	4787	1847	655
19	AWKA NORTH	755	1908	840	381
20	ANAMBRA WEST	1233	1918	1401	357
21	NNEWI SOUTH	1307	3243	226	1327
	Total	43, 285	112, 229	53, 807	21, 261

SOURCE: ABS, www.facebook.com/absradiotv.com.

Table 3: The Parties, Candidates and their votes scored

S/N	PARTY	CANDIDATE	VOTES SCORED
1	ACCORD	Godwin Maduka	2054
2	AA	Etiaba Chukwuogo	83
3	AAC	Nwankwo Chidozie	588
4	ADC	Akachukwu Nwankpo	324
5	ADP	Afam Ume-Ezeoke	773
6	APC	Andy Uba	43, 283
7	APGA	Chukwuma Soludo	112, 229
8	APP	Azubuike Echetebe	139
9	APM	OnyejegbuOkwudili	301
10	BP	Chika Okeke	186
11	LP	Emmanuel Agbasimalo	2, 802
12	NNPP	Ohajimkpo Emeka	117
13	NRM	Ezenwafor Victor	213
14	PDP	Valentine Ozigbo	53, 807
15	PRP	Nnamdi Nwawuo	437
16	SDP	Obinna Uzor	842
17	YPP	Ifeanyi Ubah	21, 261
18	ZLP	Obiora Okonwo	2, 082

Source: Vanguard, November 11, 2021, P. 4

The outcomes of the November 6, 2021 governorship election in Anambra State as stated in the table above shows the transparency, free, fair and credible conduct of the election by the Commission. It is as a result of recent innovations (BVAs Machine) introduced in the conduct of election which was experimented in Anambra State governorship election that brought credibility and transparency in the commission's image and integrity. The registered voters in Anambra State was 2, 466, 638, the accredited voters in the governorship election stood at 253, 388, valid votes was 241, 523, rejected votes was 8108, while the total votes cast in the election was 249, 631. However, APGA has been handed the mandate to rule Anambra State for another four years making twenty (20) unbroken years in power.

Table 4: Voters' turnout in the past Polls since 1999

S/NO	Year	Registered Voters	Voters Turnout	Percentage
1	1999	2, 221, 384	1, 029, 815	46.40%
2	2003	1, 859, 795	878, 212	47.22%
3	2010	1, 844, 815	301, 232	16.33%
4	2013	1, 776, 167	465, 891	26.23%
5	2017	2, 064, 134	457, 511	22.16%
6	2021	2, 466, 638	253, 388	10.27%

Source: Vanguard, November 11, 2021, P.4

The State has had the good fortune of producing not just eminent Nigerians from all works of life, men with global appeal, but also Politicians with cross-cultural appeal, individuals whose ideas and politics resonate well with both the Igbo and Nigerians. They produced the great Nnamdi Azikiwe, and the Ikemba himself, Odumegwu Ojukwu, among others. Prof. Chukwuma Soludo trounced his main challengers so comprehensively in both the main and supplementary Polls by taking 19 out of the States 21 Local Government Areas. The Governor-elect Charles Chukwuma Soludo is full of radical social ideas and developmental models, not to say the passion, to remake Anambra and turn it into a national model. There can be no gainsaying that the election reflects the overwhelming sacred mandate of Ndi Anambra and a clarion call to exemplary service. The major winners of the governorship election include Ndi Anambra, the INEC, APGA, Prof. Chukwuma Soludo, Military and Security Formations while the major losers include APC (Andy Ubah), Chris Ngige, Peter Obi, Uche Ekwunife. For the avoidance of any doubt, the constituencies of the affected individual losers were as follows: Peter Obi (Anaocha LGA), Ngige (Idemili North and South LGAs) Andy Uba (Aguata, Orumba North and South LGAs) and Ekwunife (Njikoka LGA).

IMPLICATIONS FOR THE ELECTIONS

The increasing attacks could render the election less free and fair. Violence risks undermining the electoral process in a number of ways as we argued in the paper. Firstly, the violence could lead to shortages of electoral officials. Secondly, logistics could be compromised, endangering the supply of electoral materials.

Thirdly, voters could be scared away by violence on election days. Presidential candidates might then struggle to get the votes that the constitution requires. Section 139 of Nigeria's constitution states that a presidential candidate must secure the highest number of votes cast at the election. He or she must get at least a quarter of the votes cast in each of at least two-thirds of all the states in the Federation and the Federal Capital Territory.

If candidates were unable to meet the constitutional requirements, there might have to be a rerun. That would increase the cost of election in a nation battling with high cost of governance.

The electoral prospects of the presidential candidate of the Labour Party, Peter Obi, who is from the south-east region, would be the worst hit by a very low voter turnout. He has been projected in the opinion poll to win Nigeria's 2023 presidential election, according to a poll conducted in December 2022.

In one of the pre-election polls he led with 68% in the south-east, 46% in the neighbouring south-south.

If the government and state security forces don't curb the violence in the south-east, Obi's performance at the poll could suffer.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Security is normally a priority concern of every nation and a fundamental issue of the national survival as a viable entity. Today, in Nigeria, citizens cannot sleep with their two eyes closed due to non-existence of effective security of life and property. This is because electoral Victory now belongs to the “Spoilt,” since thuggery and bloodshed were used to achieve electoral Victory. Uba (2021: 27) lamented that “sit-at-home” orders by IPOB have gravely affected the economy of the South East and had often led to the killing of flouters, arson and assassination of notable persons by a terror group called unknown gunmen. The sit-at-home orders are medium of expression of solidarity to the detained defendant (Nnamdi Kanu-IPOB) and same has been hijacked by unknown criminal elements who were terrorising the South East and engaging in wanton killings, assassinations and burning of valuable properties.

No fewer than twelve (12) INEC Offices in at least Seven States were gutted by fire with facilities completely or partially destroyed in the year 2021 alone. The situation was so bad that in a space of one month, between April and May 2021, a total of eleven (11) Offices of the Commission were either raised or Vandalized with the situation in the South East geopolitical zone particularly becoming a source of concern. The spate of arson and vandalisation targeting the commission’s facilities and property has become a major threat to the scheduled activities and the entire electoral process. In the last years, the commission has recorded a total of 41 incidents involving deliberate attacks on the commission’s facilities. Nine of these incidents happened in 2019 and 21 cases in 2020. In the last four weeks, 11 offices of the Commission were either set Ablaze or Vandalised. Two of these incidents were caused by Boko Haram and Bandit attacks while 10 resulted from thuggery during election and Post election violence. However, the majority of the attacks (29 out of 41) were unrelated to election or electoral activities. In fact, 18 of them occurred during the EndSARS protests in October 2020 while 11 attacks were Organised by Unknown gunmen and hoodlums (Yakubu, 2021).

Assessing the magnitude of the damage, the preliminary assessments so far indicate the Commission lost 1, 105 ballot boxes, 694 Voting Cubicles, 429 Electric generating sets and 13 Utility Vehicles (Toyota Hilux). These attacks, which initially appeared as isolated and occasional actions, became more frequent and systematically targeted at demobilising and dismantling critical electoral infrastructure in the Country. This will not only undermine the Commission’s capacity to organise elections and other electoral activities but will also damage the nation’s electoral process and democracy. Indeed, these attacks on the Commission’s facilities should now be treated as a national Security emergency. Apparently, the conduct and outcome of the Anambra State governorship election is one area the Commission received more commendations than attacks or criticisms. It was an election laced with multiplicity of challenges ranging from tense insecurity situation in the South East, litigations, technological experimentation, apathy, to destruction of INEC facilities and Offices before and during the Poll. Assessing the conclusion of the Anambra governorship election, despite the challenging security situation in the state, the commission was resolute in their determination to proceed with what many believed was going to be an impossible election to conduct. Happily, the election passed off peacefully and the outcome was judged to be free, fair, transparent and credible (Yakubu, 2021:13).

The Commission’s drive to fully deploy the technology in the conduct of elections has been one area it showed high-level determination, from the Smart Card Reader (SCR) and Z-pad technology it used during the conduct of the Edo and Ondo governorship elections 2020, the Commission scaled up the innovation towards making the outcome of elections more credible and acceptable with the use of Bimodal Voter Accreditation System (BVAS), during both the Isoko South, Delta State constituency and the Anambra state governorship elections. One of the areas the commission scored a Pass Mark in the year 2021 was certainly in the Creation and expansion of Polling units in the Country. Previously, there have been requests and appeals from Nigerians to the Commission to relocate many of the Polling Units situated at inappropriate places such as Private residences and properties/places of traditional rulers and places of worship to Public buildings that will be accessible to Voters, Polling agents, Observers and the media during elections. In responding to the demand this year, 2021, the Commission had at the end of the exercise, relocated a total number of 749 Polling Units from their inappropriate locations in various

states and the Federal Capital Territory (FCT). Of this figure, 232 were removed from private properties, 145 royal palaces, 6 mosques, 21 Churches and 9 Shrines. The remaining 336 Polling Units were relocated for various reasons which includes distance, difficult terrain, Congestion, communal conflict, new settlements and general insecurity.

The Commission (INEC) is certainly one of the institutions that experienced an admixture of sunshine and turbulence, in equal proportion, in the year 2021. From the colossal damage to several of its offices and facilities across the country especially from the faceless miscreants in the South East geopolitical Zone, the spill-over of the unending litigations concerning the de-registration of Political Parties to its perceived bias in the leadership crisis rocking the Inter-Party Advisory Council (IPAC) and more importantly, some technological hitches it encountered during the conduct of various off-season and by-elections, the challenges to its operations in 2021 were enormous. Then, on the flip side, the commission graduated from the perennial problems of inconclusive elections to successful conduct of several off-season Polls including the November 6, 2021 Anambra State governorship election, adjudged free, fair and credible, the improvement and millage recorded in the use of technology in the conduct of elections. It followed the year's success stories with the provision of legal framework and legislative assistance for the enactment of the now accepted Electoral Amendment Bill, which will back the Commission towards full deployment of technology in the conduct of major and minor elections in the country. The Electoral bill was signed into Law by President Buhari on Friday 25th February 2022. The resumption of continuous Voters Registration (CVR) was another gladdening news across the country in the year (2021) under review. Providing almost a near perfect logistics with smooth transmission from the online to physical capturing, the CVR was one activity most Voters applauded the Commission for a smooth operation and delivery.

In any election, authorities take steps to ensure that voters, candidates, Poll workers, Observers, and other actors involved in an election experience the process free from fear or harm and to ensure that sensitive election materials are kept secured. The specific security requirements for a given election will vary greatly depending on the context. In places with ongoing conflict, or where there is a significant potential for violence, securing an election will need to address a multiplicity of factors and will likely involve deploying relatively large numbers of security personnel from police, NSCDC or Military forces, to protect physical locations and individuals. In every election, there will be plans in place for the security, transfer and storage of election materials, especially ballots and ballot boxes. Safeguards to any technologies used in the election process should also be adopted to prevent hacking or manipulation (USAID, 2013).

The All Progressive Congress (APC) Candidate, Andy Uba, failed abysmally, not just because he was an inferior candidate compared to Soludo but partly because he spent time and energy focusing on Abuja and how he would mainstream the state into centre politics. What he never understood was that the people were not interested in Abuja which they rightly or wrongly perceived as oppressive. He never took time to address the real life and problems of the people. Prof. Chukwuma Soludo on the other hand spent his time engaging with the people and addressing their real-life situations and problems (Aguiyi, 2021:20). However, for 16years, Anambra politics has demonstrated a rare but unique pattern. The state has delivered APGA in all of her local elections. They had traditionally voted APGA consistently in the governorship and House of Assembly elections and voted PDP in Presidential elections.

The issues in the Anambra state governorship history from 1999 Politics, when Chinwoke Mbadinuju served as Anambra State Governor between May 1999 and 2003, he spent the better part of his tenure wrestling with his Political godfather (sponsor), Emeka Offor, However, midway into his four years tenure, Anambra was turned into wrestling arena in which the spectators, Ordinary People of the State, suffered enormous economic and psychological damage, financial deprivations, and mental bruises. Teachers and Public servants were owed many months of unpaid salaries. The exit of Mbadinuju and Offor in 2003 produced yet another incredible duo, Chris Ngige and his lawless godfather. For three years, Ngige and his godfather took their personal quarrels to the streets of Awka and a shrine in Okija, where their supporters engaged in regular shootouts. When Ngige was Ousted by an Appeal Court

decision and Peter Obi was declared the rightful winner of the 2003 governorship election that Ngige had claimed wrongfully, everyone thought the drama in Anambra State had ended, but everyone was wrong. Hardly had Peter Obi settled down to serve his tenure than a band of legislators in the State House of Assembly impeached him. However, like a child of fortune, Peter Obi was later restored to his job by an Appeal Court judgement (Obijiofor, 2021:32). Willie Obiano was elected governor in 2013 and re-elected for second tenure in 2017 while in 2021 Prof. Chukwuma Charles Soludo was elected governor Anambra State.

In the face of this growing Security challenge, in the first half of the year 2021 alone, out of 2, 943 incidents of kidnapping in Nigeria, 2, 557 took place in Northern Nigeria, with the North West alone recording the highest cases of 1, 405. Similarly, of the over 5, 800 killings recorded in Nigeria between January and June 2021, Northern States like Borno, Zamfara, Kaduna, Niger, Katsina and Kebbi, with 1, 137, 862, 715, 407, 164 and 144 deaths were top of the list of human slaughter slabs in Nigeria. In addition to kidnapping, robbery and mass killings, killer herdsmen were in control of vast swaths of ungoverned territories, where they exercise pseudo authority and forcefully extract taxes and levies from farmers before they plant in their farms or harvested their crops (Dahiru, 2021:32). Apart from what is happening in Northern Nigeria, one can recall the evidence of Political injustice, unfairness, marginalization of the Igbo extraction in the affairs of our Country are crystal clear. This perceived Political injustice to the Igbos is particularly evidence since advent of our nascent democracy in 1999, the Igbos have unable to produce any of his highly qualified and industrious sons or daughters at the seat of power in Aso Rock, Abuja, Nigeria. Unlike the other two major ethnic groups in Nigeria, namely the Hausas and Yorubas, the Igbos dream of ruling the Country, still remains a tall order (Ojo, 2021:12).

RECOMMENDATIONS

We must remind ourselves that modern states are created on social contracts, for, left in the Original State of nature, Societies Ordinarily descend to a Hobbesian State, where life is solitary, poor, nasty, brutish and short. To avert such endless state of anomie, citizens surrender some of their rights and subject themselves to sovereigns or authority of leaders elected by them, in exchange for their security and welfare. Consequently, in Nigeria's case, Section 14 (2) (b) of the 1999 constitution (as amended) unequivocally provides that "the Security and welfare of the people shall be the Primary purpose of government. The state of insecurity in Anambra State in bid to the preparation of governorship election was dire, and everyone was baffled by the high rate of cold-blooded murders committed on the streets by unidentified people. The state was hijacked by gun-wielding men and women who shoot randomly at people without asking questions. How did Anambra State descend to this low point, a situation in which people were hunted openly brutally murdered and abandoned like animals in the street or bush. The following recommendations are necessary to checkmate the causes of electoral insecurity in the conduct of off-cycle governorship election in Nigeria:

- (a) We strongly advocate for adequate electoral Security that will enhance the free, fair and credible conduct of elections. Electoral Security should ensure free movement of staff, voters, candidates, observers and other stakeholders in the election process. It is painful when lives are lost during the election, because no matter the grievances of those involved in political contest, nothing justifies the cold blooded murder of an innocent official conducting a legitimate national assignment intended to afford the citizen an opportunity to freely choose their leader. The insecurity is very unfortunate and it could be ascribe to the failure of government in the country. The principal obligation of every government is to provide for the welfare and safety of citizen.
- (b) We must stop marginalization of any section of the Country, the end product is the aggressive agitation for secession from the country. We cannot deny the fact that such inconsiderate policies must have given birth to many of the pockets of insecurity that are weighing down the country today.

- (c) All lover of democracy should continue to support the use of technology in the elections as a proactive move to strengthen the foundations of democracy in Nigeria. The case for the use of electronic transmission of results is unassailable because it encourages openness, fairness and offers every political party and candidate a level playing field. The effort of the Independent National Electoral Commission (INEC) in introducing technological innovations-Bimodal Voter Accreditation system (BVAS) for accrediting voters using fingerprint and facial capture and equally used to scan election results and to transmit (upload) to the INEC server (portal) in Abuja should be encouraged and supported by the public.
- (d) The frequent and systematic way, the destruction of INEC critical electoral infrastructure or facilities was carried out by unidentified person(s) should be checkmated by the Security agencies using the technological gadgets such as CCTV Camera install in all Commission Offices both at the state and local government area offices. This destruction will not only undermine the commission's capacity to organise elections and other electoral activities but will also damage the nation's electoral process and democracy.
- (e) The Political Parties should stop abusing the system of internal democracy because greatest problem confronting parties today are traceable to non-adherence to democratic rules in the conduct of internal affairs of the political parties in Nigeria. The Political class (Politician) should play the rules of the game by discouraging the imposition of candidates during party primaries. The internal bad governance of the parties is a critical issue which if unchecked could derail any democratic government.
- (f) The best solution to solve the Biafran and IPOB question is to treat the Igbo as co-owners of Nigeria. The Igbos are not asking for too much, what the Igbo need is justice and equity. There is nothing wrong if the federal Government sets up a committee to negotiate with IPOB and listen to their grievances, because the government has been negotiating with insurgents.

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